

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON DISTINGUISHING PLUNDERING FROM FRAUD

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Today, in order to accelerate the state's property protection function, special attention is paid to the issues of prevention of any encroachment on property rights, fight against them, identification of problems encountered in this field in the practice of law enforcement, and improvement of criminal law norms in this regard.

Property of others in the criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan criminal liability is established for various methods of robbery, and these norms serve to protect property relations. Also, in the practice of applying the law, there are problems related to the classification of crimes related to the robbery of other people's property, and their differentiation from each other. One of them is robbery without violence (Article 166, Part 1) is distinguished from fraud. After all, fraud committed by "cheating" is objectively similar to robbery committed without the use of force, so there are a number of problems in distinguishing between them.

In accordance with paragraph 3 of the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice in the criminal cases of theft, robbery and robbery of other people's property by invasion" as open robbery, the culprit, the victim and others take over the property of another in front of others. and when they realize that he understands the criminal nature of his actions, he is told to openly plunder another's property¹.

It is known that the disposition of Article 168 of the Criminal Code defines fraud as "acquiring another's property or the right to another's property by deception or abuse of trust." Deception in fraud is defined as deliberate actions by the guilty party, which knowingly report false information that is not true, or conceal the true facts that should be reported to the owner, other owner of the property, or mislead such persons².

According to paragraph 14 of the decision of the plenum of the supreme court of the republic of uzbekistan "on judicial practice in cases related to fraud" of

¹ The decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice in criminal cases of theft, robbery and robbery of other people's property by invasion" [Electronic source] <https://www.lex.uz/docs/1448644> (time of application: 16.10.2021)

² Resolution No. 35 of October 11, 2017, of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice in cases related to fraud" [Electronic source] <https://www.lex.uz/docs/3399888> (accessed: 16.10.2021)

october 11, 2017, no. 35, if deception was used by a person to facilitate the acquisition of another's property, and in the process of confiscating the property, the owner, owner of the property or another person has sensed his original intention, even if the culprit understands it, but continues to keep the property against the will of the owner or owner of the property, the act should be qualified as robbery, and in cases where the property is hidden with the property without informing the owner or owner of the property, it should be qualified as fraud³.

We have seen above that there are legal grounds for differentiating these crimes, but today's judicial investigation practice mainly refers to the cases of taking someone else's movable property, i.e., mobile phone, jewelry, and similar items from the victim for temporary use or purchase, to inspect the property, and to escape and hide. There are problems in clarifying.

In order to openly rob other people's property, the preliminary investigation body tricked N.Sh. by telling him to give F.N. cash in cash on December 23, 2014, Navoi city, X .D. street, 54, took his plastic cards and said that he would go to an acquaintance to cash them, and so that they would not have to wait, he openly took the "Nokia S-2" phone with a price of 300,000 soums belonging to F.N. of the CRIMINAL CODE of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the case of looting and running away from the scene of the incident He was charged with part 1 of Article 166.

However, the court considered that the purpose of the defendant N.Sh in this case was to acquire another's property through fraud and abuse of trust, and rejected the assessment of the act as open robbery, declaring the criminal action of the defendant N.Sh to be a crime of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 166 of the Civil Code, Part 1, Article 168 of the Civil Code Requalified for Part⁴ [4].

In addition, the preliminary investigation body K.X.Q, on May 15, 2018 at 12:00, for the purpose of obtaining another's property by means of deception and abuse of trust, "BMW-730" with registration number 01 Q 771 KA under his control In a car with model No. 1, he came to Katta Mirabad street, Mirabad district, after removing the rear license plate, citizen A.D.S. meeting with D. Ataniyazov, transferring the same amount of electronic title tokens equal to 7,000 US dollars from his "Web Money" account number to his "Gogex" account number, and not fulfilling his promise to D. Ataniyazov, hiding from the scene of the incident, Article 166, Part 2 "b" of the Criminal Code qualified with clause. The court assessed the circumstances of the case and concluded that the transfer

³ That source

⁴ From the archives of the Navoi city court on criminal cases. Criminal case No. 1-487/16.

of the electronic signs, which were considered the property of D.A., to the account of X.Q. was carried out voluntarily, that there was a mutual agreement between them, and that the case of forced possession of the title signs, which were the personal property of D.A., was not confirmed in court. and because the sale of electronic signs recognized as property has already taken place between them, X.K.'s actions are based on the signs of open robbery of another's property in a large amount from Article 166, Part 2, Clause "b" of the Criminal Code, obtaining a large amount of another's property by means of fraud, that is, deception and abuse of trust, computer equipment reclassified to clauses "a", "v" of Article 168, Part 2 of the Civil Code with signs of abuse ⁵.

In both of the above cases, the legal evaluation of the act was qualified without specifying the actions of the perpetrator aimed at taking property from the victim. As a result, the legal assessment given by the preliminary investigation body was thoroughly studied by the court and reclassified to another article.

Being a dangerous recidivist, on May 4, 2020 at 4:00 p.m., on the banks of the "Tashlamasoi" canal located on Al-Khorazmi Street in Ferghana, M.X allegedly called the phone of the minor J.E. worth 1,700,000 soums "Samsung A10S" CRIMINAL CODE's state of running away pretending to be talking on the phone after asking for it

Qualified by Article 166, Part 1. In this case, the preliminary investigation body came to the correct conclusion. Because, although the culprit obtained the property by deception, the started fraud was not completed, and the victim noticed his criminal intention and could not pursue him.

In conclusion, it should be said that when distinguishing robbery from fraud, the main attention should be focused on clarifying the motive, purpose, actions and behavior of the perpetrator aimed at acquiring property, as well as the actions of the victim after handing over the property.

⁵ From the archives of the Mirabad district criminal court of Tashkent city. Criminal case No. 1-1002-1903/98.